

DEVELOPMENT OF MULTISCALE DAMAGE PROPAGATION ANALYSIS METHOD FOR WOVEN LAMINATES USING A HOMOGENIZATION THEORY

G. Kubo¹ and T. Matsuda²

¹ Department of Engineering Mechanics and Energy, University of Tsukuba, Tsukuba, Japan, s1730189@s.tsukuba.ac.jp

² Department of Engineering Mechanics and Energy, University of Tsukuba, Tsukuba, Japan, matsuda@kz.tsukuba.ac.jp

Keywords: Woven laminate, Damage propagation, Strength, Homogenization theory, Laminate misalignment

ABSTRACT

In this study, damage behavior/strength properties of plain- and 2×2 twill-woven laminates and their dependence on laminates misalignment are investigated. For this, novel unit cells which are smaller than previous unit cells and boundary conditions for homogenization analysis are proposed for the purpose of reducing a calculation load. Failure criterion is then introduced into the theory to determine the failure of fiber bundles and a matrix material, and the damage modes. According to the damage modes, the damages are expressed as reduction of stiffness based on damage mechanics. This method is then applied to the damage propagation analysis of two woven laminates with several laminate misalignments including the non-misaligned cases under on-axis uniaxial tension. It is shown that the laminate misalignment noticeably affects the macroscopic strength of the laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

Woven laminates are fabricated by impregnating stacked weaving fabrics with polymer materials. These laminates are classified by types of weaving fabrics such as plain-, twill-fabrics, and are referred to as plain-, twill-woven laminates, respectively. Because of their good features, e.g. light weight, high strength and good formability, they have been more and more often used as structural members in various industrial fields. It is thus important to accurately predict their damage behaviour and strength. For this, unit cell analyses were conducted using FEM or homogenization method in the previous studies [1-5]. According to them [2-4], it was shown that microscopic damage behaviour of plain-woven laminates were affected by "laminate misalignment", which was a shift between stacked fabric layers, resulting in the considerable change of macroscopic strength of plain-woven laminates. Although such analysis has been performed for plain- and twill-woven laminates, these analysis domains generally become quite large owing to their complicated weaving structures. Consequently high computational costs are needed for inelastic analysis. This is one of the technical problem being solved.

In this study, first, novel unit cells smaller than previous ones and boundary conditions for homogenization analysis for a 2×2 twill-woven laminate with laminate misalignment are proposed to reduce computational costs. Second, the Hoffman's failure criterion is introduced into the homogenization theory to determine failure of fiber bundles and a matrix material, and the damage modes. According to the damage modes, the damages are expressed as reduction of stiffness based on damage mechanics [2]. This method is then applied to the damage propagation analysis of plain-, 2×2 twill-woven glass fibre-reinforced plastic (GFRP) laminates with several laminate misalignments including non-misaligned cases under on-axis uniaxial tension. From the results of analysis, effects of the laminate misalignment on the damage propagation behavior/strength properties of the laminates are examined.

2 HOMOGENIZATION THEORY FOR WOVEN LAMINATE WITH LAMINATE MISALIGNMENT

Due to space limitation, let us omit explanation of the homogenization theory for a plain-woven laminate [6] and start with the theory for a 2×2 twill -woven laminate with laminate misalignment.

2.1 Analysis domain of 2×2 twill -woven laminate in the in-plane direction

Let us consider a 2×2 twill-woven laminate and the Cartesian coordinates y_i ($i=1,2,3$) as illustrated in Fig. 1, and define its basic cell A as the analysis domain. The boundary of A is divided into 5 parts as depicted Fig. 1(a). On the Γ_{A_1} , the microstructure of the 2×2 twill-woven laminate is found to be periodic. In contrast, the structure is found to be point-symmetric with respect to the central point on the Γ_{A_2} . In the same way as Γ_{A_2} , the microstructure possesses the point-symmetries with respect to the centers of $\Gamma_{A_3} \sim \Gamma_{A_5}$.

2.2 Analysis domain of woven laminates with laminate misalignment in the thickness direction

Second, let us explain the case of a 2×2 twill -woven laminate with laminate misalignment in the thickness direction. As depicted Fig. 1(b), the microstructure in $y_2 - y_3$ plane possesses the point-symmetries with respect to the centers of Γ_{A_6} and Γ_{A_7} , and periodicity on Γ_{A_8} . In the same way in $y_2 - y_3$ plane, the microstructure possesses the point-symmetries and periodicity in $y_1 - y_2$ plane. Namely, the boundary conditions for woven laminates including plain- and 2×2 twill-woven laminates with laminate misalignment are expressed as the combination of point-symmetries and periodicities.

It should be noted that the present modeling method, including the boundary conditions, enables us to substantially reduce the analysis domain for woven laminates with laminate misalignment compared with the previous modeling methods [1-5].

2.3 Homogenization theory considering thermal strain

A constitutive equation of constituents in the basic cells is expressed in a rate form as

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijkl} (\dot{\epsilon}_{kl} + \Delta T \alpha_{kl}), \quad (1)$$

where c_{ijkl} and α_{kl} represents the elastic stiffness and the coefficient of thermal expansion satisfying $c_{ijkl} = c_{jikl} = c_{ijlk} = c_{klij}$ and $\alpha_{kl} = \alpha_{lk}$, and $\dot{\epsilon}_{kl}$ indicates the microscopic strain rate.

As already described in the previous subsection 2.1 and 2.2, we impose the point-symmetric and periodic boundary conditions on the basic cells, and obtain the following evolution equation of σ_{ij} and the relation between macroscopic stress rate $\dot{\Sigma}_{ij}$ and strain rate \dot{E}_{kl} :

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijkl} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \dot{E}_{kl} - \Delta T c_{ijkl} (\alpha_{kl} + \psi_{k,l}), \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{\Sigma}_{ij} = \langle c_{ijkl} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \rangle \dot{E}_{kl} - \Delta T \langle c_{ijkl} (\alpha_{kl} + \psi_{k,l}) \rangle, \quad (3)$$

where χ_i^{kl} , ψ_i are the characteristic functions obtained by solving the following boundary problems

Fig.1 Basic cell of 2×2 twill-woven laminate with laminate misalignment and its cross section.

$$\int_V c_{ijpq} \chi_{p,q}^{kl} v_{i,j} dV = - \int_V c_{ijkl} v_{i,j} dV, \quad (4)$$

$$\int_V c_{ijpq} \psi_{p,q} v_{i,j} dV = \int_V c_{ijkl} \alpha_{kl} v_{i,j} dV, \quad (5)$$

δ_{ij} indicates Kronecker's delta, $v_{i,j}$ represents an variation of the perturbed velocity field in V , and $\langle \# \rangle$ stands for the volume average in V , i.e. $\langle \# \rangle = |V|^{-1} \int_V \# dV$, where $|V|$ signifies the volume of V .

3 DAMAGE PROPAGATION ANALYSIS

3.1 Failure criterion and classification of damage modes

In this study, the Hoffman's failure criterion [7] is introduced into the above-mentioned homogenization theory to determine the fracture of fiber bundles and a matrix material. This criterion is described using the current stress state as follows:

$$F = C_1 (\sigma_T - \sigma_Z)^2 + C_2 (\sigma_Z - \sigma_L)^2 + C_3 (\sigma_L - \sigma_T)^2 + C_4 \sigma_L + C_5 \sigma_T + C_6 \sigma_Z + C_7 \sigma_{TZ}^2 + C_8 \sigma_{ZL}^2 + C_9 \sigma_{LT}^2, \quad (6)$$

where the lower indices L, T and Z respectively denote the local coordinates for the fiber direction, the transverse direction, and the perpendicular direction to the L- and T-directions, and $\sigma_{(\cdot)}$ stands for the stress in the local coordinates. Moreover, $C_1 - C_9$ in Eq. (6) indicate the material parameters which depend on the tensile, compressive, and shear strength in the local coordinates. At each time step in the analysis, F at every finite element in a basic cell is calculated based on Eq. (6), and the element in which F reaches 1 is considered to be damaged.

Fiber bundles are considered to have 6 kinds of damage modes as listed in Table 1, which are classified into 4 types of damages described as Fig. 2 [2, 3]. Thus, if F reaches 1 at a finite element in a fiber bundle, we have to determine which damage mode has occurred at the element. For this, we calculate the stress to strength ratios listed in Table 1 at the element. Then, the damage mode corresponding to the highest ratio is determined to occur.

3.2 Failure expression based on damage mechanics

In this subsection, let us explain the anisotropy failure expression corresponded to the aforementioned damage modes based on damage mechanics. The damaged elastic stiffness matrix $[C']$ is described as follows:

$$[C'] = \begin{bmatrix} d_L^2 C_{11} & d_L d_T C_{12} & d_L d_Z C_{12} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & d_T^2 C_{22} & d_T d_Z C_{23} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & d_Z^2 C_{33} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & d_{TZ} C_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ & sym. & & & d_{ZL} C_{55} & 0 \\ & & & & & d_{LT} C_{66} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (7)$$

where C_{ij} denotes each component of the undamaged elastic stiffness matrix, and d_{ij} is defined using damage value D_i as

$$d_L = 1 - D_L, d_T = 1 - D_T, d_Z = 1 - D_T, \\ d_{TZ} = \left(\frac{2d_T d_Z}{d_T + d_Z} \right)^2, d_{ZL} = \left(\frac{2d_Z d_L}{d_Z + d_L} \right)^2, d_{LT} = \left(\frac{2d_L d_T}{d_L + d_T} \right)^2, \quad (8)$$

Here, D_i corresponds to the aforementioned damage modes as described in Table 1, and is assumed to be 0 (undamaged) or 1 (damaged) in this study. Therefore if each finite element in fiber bundles is damaged, we recalculate the elastic stiffness c_{ijkl} using Eq. (7) and (8) according to damage mode. For

more detail on the computational procedure, see [2].

4 ANALYSIS CONDITIONS

4.1 Basic cells, material parameters and laminate misalignment

The basic cells *A* and *B*, which were much smaller than the unit cells in the previous studies[1-5], were respectively defined for plain- and 2×2 twill-woven GFRP laminates as shown in Fig. 3, and were divided into finite elements by referring [6]. It is noted that either basic cell has the same volume fraction of fiber bundles (44 %). The fiber bundles were regarded as E-glass/vinylester unidirectional composites and transversely isotropic elastic materials, while the matrix was vinylester, which was regarded as an isotropic elastic material. Their material parameters are set as listed in Table 2 by referring the previous study [3, 8, 9]. Now, introducing (*a*, *b*) as the amount of laminate misalignment in the y_3 - y_1 plane, 13 and 23 cases of (*a*, *b*) are considered for *A* and *B*, as shown in Figs. 4, 5 respectively.

4.2 Analysis procedure and loading condition

First, we conducted the thermal residual stress analysis of woven laminates in the cooling period of manufacturing process. The laminates were subjected to a macroscopic temperature change from

Table1 Damage modes of fiber bundles.

Damage mode	L	T	LT	Z	ZL	TZ
Stress to strength ratios	$\frac{\sigma_L^2}{F_L^t F_L^c}$	$\frac{\sigma_T^2}{F_T^t F_T^c}$	$\left(\frac{\tau_{LT}}{F_{LT}^s}\right)^2$	$\frac{\sigma_Z^2}{F_Z^t F_Z^c}$	$\left(\frac{\tau_{ZL}}{F_{ZL}^s}\right)^2$	$\left(\frac{\tau_{TZ}}{F_{TZ}^s}\right)^2$
Damage value	$D_L = 1$ $D_T = 0$ $D_Z = 0$	$D_L = 0$ $D_T = 1$ $D_Z = 0$	$D_L = 0$ $D_T = 1$ $D_Z = 0$	$D_L = 0$ $D_T = 0$ $D_Z = 1$	$D_L = 0$ $D_T = 0$ $D_Z = 1$	$D_L = 0$ $D_T = 1$ $D_Z = 1$

Fig. 2 4 types of damages in fiber bundles ; (a) mode L, (b) mode T & TL, (c) mode Z & ZL, (d) mode TZ.

Fig.3 Basic cells of woven GFRP composites and their finite element meshes; (a) plain (nodes: 2499, elements: 2048), (b) 2×2 twill (nodes: 4899, elements: 4096).

Fig.4 Laminate misalignment of plain-woven laminates.

Fig.5 Laminate misalignment of 2×2 twill-woven laminates.

Table 2 Material constants of fiber bundles and vinylester [3, 8, 9].

	Fiber bundles (E-glass-Vinylester)	Vinylester
Young's modulus [GPa]	E_L 42.80 E_T 12.22 E_Z 12.22	E 3.334
Shear modulus [GPa]	G_{TZ} 4.872 G_{ZL} 4.775 G_{LT} 4.775	G 1.282
Poisson's ratio	ν_{TZ} 0.254 ν_{ZL} 0.067 ν_{LT} 0.233	ν 0.300
Tensile strength [MPa]	F_L^t 2024.0 F_T^t 108.2 F_Z^t 108.2	F^t 88.26
Compressive strength [MPa]	F_L^c 2982.0 F_T^c 242.3 F_Z^c 242.3	F^c 117.7
Shear strength [MPa]	F_{TZ}^s 50.0 F_{ZL}^s 73.0 F_{LT}^s 73.0	F^s 88.26
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion(CTE)[$10^{-6}/K$]	α_L 7.09 α_T 40.5 α_Z 40.5	α 70.0

100°C to 20°C. No external force was given to the laminates, that is, $\dot{\Sigma}_{ij} = 0$, and there was no macroscopic constraint. We obtained microscopic thermal residual stress and the deformation in each finite element model. After that, inputting the stress and the deformation as initial conditions, we conducted damage propagation analysis of the laminates. The laminates were subjected to uniaxial tension in the y_3 -direction at a constant strain rate at room temperature until macroscopic strain E_{33} reaches 2.0 %.

5 RESULTS OF ANALYSIS

Fig. 6 (a) and (b) respectively show the macroscopic stress-strain relations of plain- and 2×2 twill-woven laminates with laminate misalignment. It is found from the figure that the stress levels at damage initiation and sudden stress drops considerably vary depending on the misalignment, and that this dependence is affected by the difference of weaving structures in spite of the same volume fraction of fiber bundles in the basic cells.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, effects of laminate misalignment on the strength of plain- and 2×2 twill-woven laminates are investigated. For this, novel unit cells and boundary conditions expressed as a combination of point-symmetries and periodicities for homogenization analysis were proposed to reduce calculation load. Failure criterion and damage express methodology in the prior research [2] were then introduced into the theory. It should be noted that the present method enabled us to substantially reduce the analysis domain for the homogenization analysis of the woven laminates with laminate misalignment compared with the previous methods. This is eminently suitable for nonlinear analysis accompanied by incremental computation e.g. the damage propagation analysis as performed in this study. This method was then applied to the damage propagation analysis of two woven

Fig.6 Macroscopic stress-strain relations of woven GFRP laminates with laminate misalignment; (a) plain (13 cases of misalignment), (b) 2×2 twill (23 cases of misalignment).

laminates with several laminate misalignments including the non-misaligned cases under on-axis uniaxial tension considering thermal residual stress occurring in manufacturing process. It was shown that the laminate misalignment noticeably affects the macroscopic strength of the laminates.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful for partial support from Japan Society for the Promotion of Science Grant-in-Aid for JSPS Research Fellow (No. 17J00708).

REFERENCES

- [1] N. Takano, Y. Uetsuji, Y. Kashiwagi and M. Zako, Hierarchical modeling of textile composite materials and structures by the homogenization method, *Modelling and Simulation in Materials Science and Engineering*, **7**, 1999, pp. 207-231.
- [2] M. Zako, Y. Uetsuji, and T. Kurashiki, Finite element analysis of damaged woven fabric composite materials, *Composites Science and Technology*, **63**, 2003, pp.507-516.
- [3] Y. Uetsuji, Y. Ishiwari, M. Zako, T. Kurashiki and I. Verpoest, Effect of mismatch of stacking phase on damage development of plain woven fabric composite materials, *Journal of the Society of Materials Science*, **53**, 2004, pp.403- 409 (in Japanese).
- [4] G. Kubo and T. Matsuda, Effects of laminate misalignment on macroscopic strength and microscopic damage development of plain-woven laminates, *Mechanical Engineering Letters*, **2**, 2016, 16-00248.
- [5] D. S. Ivanov, S. G. Ivanov, S. V. Lomov and I. Verpoest, Unit cell modeling of textile laminates with arbitrary inter-ply shifts, *Composites Science and Technology*, **72**, 2011, pp. 14-20.
- [6] T. Matsuda, S. Kanamaru, N. Honda and N. Ohno, Macro/micro elastic-viscoplastic analysis of woven composite laminates with misaligned woven fabrics. *Advanced Structured Materials*, **19**, 2013, pp. 251-261.
- [7] O. Hoffman, The brittle strength of orthotropic material, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **1**, 1967, pp.200-206.
- [8] Y. Uetsuji, A. Tanioka, T. Matsuka and M. Zako, Nonlinear Finite Element Analysis of Woven Fabric Composites Considering Thermal Residual Stresses in Forming Process, *Proceeding of the JSME annual meeting*, **1**, 2007, pp. 227-228 (in Japanese).
- [9] A.S. Kaddour and M.J. Hinton, Maturity of 3D failure criteria for fibre-reinforced composites: comparison between theories and experiments: part B of WWFE-II, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **47**, 2013, pp. 925-966.